

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DIPH
COURSE CODE: ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

Edited to show actual information below:

The author applied US

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software (e.g., MS365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the difference between notes-bibliography and author-date styles in citation formats?
- The notes-bibliography style uses footnotes, while the author-date style uses in-text citations¹**
 - The notes-bibliography style uses in-text citations, while the author-date style uses footnotes
 - Both styles use footnotes for citation
 - Both styles use in-text citations for citation

¹ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition (London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 177-179.

2. According to Turabian guidelines, how should interviews and personal communications be cited in academic writing?
- Author's Name, Date of Publication, Interview Title
 - Interviewee's Name, Interview Title, Date of Interview²**
 - Author's Name, Date of Publication, Article Title
 - Interviewee's Name, Date of Publication, Interview Title
3. In the Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research, what is the significance of conducting a literature review in the research process?
- To summarize the findings of the study
 - To provide content gaps in prior research³**
 - To generate new research questions
 - To present the methodology of the study
4. How does the Turabian Rule of Style recommend handling long quotations of five lines or longer in academic writing?
- Set it without quotation marks⁴**
 - Use double quotation marks for long quotations
 - Include ellipses to indicate omitted text within the quotation

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 288.

³ James P. Sampson. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 39.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35.

- Avoid using long quotations in academic writing
5. How should chapters be labeled to maintain consistency and clarity in a dissertation?
- Label each chapter with the author's name
- Label each chapter with the publication date
- Label each chapter with the chapter number⁵**
- Label each chapter with the page numbers
6. According to the WHO Style Guide, which numbering system should be used for book or journal article footnotes?
- Roman numerals
- Superscript Arabic numerals⁶**
- Lower-case letters
- Alphanumeric characters
7. When should numbers be written in words in running text according to the WHO Style Guide?
- Zero to ninety-nine
- Zero to nine⁷**

⁵ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 39.

⁶ WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 49.

⁷ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 26.

- Zero to nineteen
 - Zero to twenty-nine
8. Which one can serve as a general guideline to avoid plagiarism?
- Using words from a source with quotation marks
 - Avoid a close paraphrase from a source
 - Restate a point in your own words
 - All of the Above⁸**
9. Which section of the dissertation should be organized by research questions rather than hypotheses in a qualitative study?
- Introduction
 - Literature Review
 - Data Analysis
 - Summary of Findings and Discussion⁹**
10. what is necessary to provide evidence of the accuracy of data analysis in qualitative research?
- including a detailed literature review
 - Citing multiple sources of data
 - Using advanced statistical software

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 14.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 49.

Independent verification by another qualified¹⁰

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Ibid., 55.